

A P O L L O

D6.6: 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report

WP6 – Pilot operation and evaluation

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Executive summary

The deliverable at hand – the 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report – provides an overview of the evaluation activities that carried out in the course of the APOLLO project at the locations of the three pilot areas and presents results and findings. The 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report consists of three chapters:

- In the first chapter, the reasoning for conducting an evaluation survey is analysed. Also, a literature review on the importance of the evaluation surveys and their possible challenges are presented. Moreover, there is reference on the impact that satellite remote sensing can have in various agricultural operations as they are found in the scientific literature.
- In the second chapter, the evaluation results are presented in terms of APOLLO service, country and crop type. Specifically, the evaluation results refer to the evaluation of APOLLO tillage and irrigation scheduling services in the pilot sites.
- The third and final chapter contains the conclusions that were derived from this evaluation survey and on the way that they will help in the business development of the APOLLO services.

1 Introduction

The main objective of the APOLLO project was to develop a commercial platform that will provide advisory services to small farmers regarding i) tillage scheduling, ii) irrigation scheduling, iii) crop growth monitoring and iv) crop yield estimation. The services are based on Earth Observation Data coming from the EU's Sentinel satellites as well as on free online databases. These data are inserted in state-of-the-art algorithms for providing valuable information to small farmers and crop consultants regarding the aforementioned services.

The commercial success of APOLLO services depend highly from its users' acceptance. However, in order achieve user acceptance, APOLLO needs showcase the benefits that it can provide to the final users. One way of doing this is through impact evaluation.

Impact evaluation assesses the changes that can be attributed to a particular intervention, such as a process, program or policy, both the intended ones, as well as ideally the unintended ones. In contrast to outcome monitoring, which examines whether targets have been achieved, impact evaluation is structured to answer the question: how would outcomes change, if the intervention had not been undertaken? This involves counterfactual analysis, that is, "a comparison between what actually happened and what would have happened in the absence of the intervention". Impact evaluations seek to answer cause-and-effect questions. In other words, they look for the changes in outcome that are directly attributable to one or more services¹.

Impact evaluations in the agriculture sector are growing in number. However, most, if not all, evaluations that have employed experimental methods have been conducted on a relatively small-scale as pilot projects, with a primary goal of learning whether certain interventions work. However, several factors make evaluation in the agriculture sector especially challenging. Specifically, these factors fall into two broad categories: 1) challenges derived from agriculture projects concept and 2) challenges derived from implementing the agriculture projects (Winters et al., 2010; IEG, 2011; Farley et al., 2012). The main challenges of each category are mentioned in Table 1.

¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Impact_evaluation

Table 1 – Challenges in Agriculture Projects according to Farley et al. (2012).

Category	Challenge	Description
Agriculture Projects Concept Challenges	Crop cycles and seasonality	The seasonality of agriculture creates two challenges related to timing. The first is the timing relative to crop cycles. Agriculture production cycles pose strict windows for when training and related activities, including fielding evaluation surveys, can occur. The second is the expected time between an intervention and the expected results. Agriculture projects often require several crop cycles to measure benefit, as farmers become proficient in new techniques, expand their application and learn from one season to the next.
	Context variables	Agriculture production is highly affected by weather, mainly temperature and rainfall. These conditions or variables change from year to year. Also, changes in market prices for agriculture products affect the returns of the intervention that the treatment group receives.
	Spillover effects	Spillover or demonstration effects, such as when people outside the primary targeted beneficiary groups adopt techniques supported by a given intervention, are sometimes expected in agriculture projects and often are a desired outcome in design that promotes faster adoption of new techniques and methods.
	Implementation changes	Even when project design is set, agriculture implementation approaches can evolve significantly over the course of a project in response to changing market conditions or more detailed implementation planning.
	Sequencing of interventions in integrated projects	For projects that include a variety of interventions, such as farmer training, access to credit, and infrastructure investments, sequencing is important for achieving the desired outcomes.
	National-level interventions	Projects that target agriculture-related national-level policy reform or institutional change, such as new water laws, credit regulations, improved phytosanitary and inspection services, and improved linkages to export channels for targeted value chains, do not generally contribute to identify already existing best practices in the country.
	Self-selection	An important constraint for the evaluation of agriculture projects is that they often include some degree of self-selection. This implies that only certain types of farmers may choose to participate in a given project, requiring the evaluation to isolate the impacts of a given intervention from the influence of unobservable characteristics, such as personal motivation, of the individuals who chose to participate.

Category	Challenge	Description
Agriculture Projects Implementation Challenges	Implications for scope	Requiring a control group that is comparable to the target population can reduce the overall reach and scope of projects. If the demand for project interventions exceeds the scope allowed by the project budget, timeline or willingness to invest in an unproven intervention, it is easier to construct a control group. However, in cases where donors and implementers are confident of the intervention's cost-effectiveness, and have the ability to reach all potential beneficiaries, there are inherent tradeoffs between project scope and learning potential.
	Implications for flexibility	Adherence to an impact evaluation methodology may limit implementers' ability to adapt implementation approaches in response to changing conditions or new information. While impact evaluations can be designed to be remarkably robust to planned ranges of implementer adaptation, an intervention with no planned structure poses a serious evaluation risk. It also may pose a significant investment risk for a donor.
	Implementers often make strong assumptions about what works and what doesn't work	Development professionals, donors, implementers, and partner countries may think they know what works. But there is strikingly little evidence available to test prevailing assumptions.
	Political sensitivities	Randomized selection of communities or beneficiaries may mean that the project may not work with all of the most promising beneficiaries, because some will be out of the selection. This may be politically challenging for program implementers or country counterparts who have to explain why some potential beneficiaries will not be able to participate in the program.
	Unclear value or costs	Implementers are sometimes given little opportunity to see the value of impact evaluations. Focused primarily on how evaluation methodologies might restrict scope or operational flexibility, agriculture implementers get little information regarding the design of impact evaluations or few opportunities to provide input into what they aim to learn.
	Conflicting incentives	Implementers often face incentives to meet targets, regardless of how this affects evaluation methodology, while evaluators have incentives to adhere to evaluation approaches, regardless of how this may limit the flexibility of implementers to adapt to changing conditions and new information.

Almost 50 years have passed since the first use of satellite data for agricultural purposes. During this period, many studies were conducted for highlighting the usefulness of satellite remote sensed data for taking decisions on field, regional, national and international level for agriculture. In example, Hassan et al. (2017) evaluated a conventional crop monitoring system with a satellite based crop monitoring system and found that the latter was almost 3 times cheaper while it saved 96 working days when compared with the former one. Calera et al. (2017) found up to 30% savings in water consumption for crops when satellite remote sensing is used for this reason compared to current irrigation practices. Moreover, satellite based application of crop nutrients such as nitrogen can present up to 35% savings when compared with current fertilization practices (Seelan et al., 2003). Skakun et al. (2016) presented a methodology for quantifying drought risk in Ukraine by using satellite data. Schemedtmann and Campagnolo (2015) presented a methodology for using satellite data in crop identification for supporting National Control and Paying Agencies for paying subsidies to farmers. Burke and Lobell (2017) used high-resolution satellite imagery and field data for estimating yield variations in small farms in Africa. Müllerová et al. (2017) used a time series satellite imagery to monitor plant invasion.

As indicated above, the satellite remote sensing data can provide important savings in time, spraying and fertilization dose while they can help protect on time crops by helping in the identification of early pests infests and diseases infestations. So, it was important for the APOLLO project to assess its offered services by evaluating the impact of their application in different crops. This document -the 2nd Intermediate Evaluation Report of APOLLO project- presents the outcomes of the application of APOLLO services in comparison with current farm practices. The survey was conducted at the pilot areas (Pella region – Greece, Ruma region – Serbia, Castilla La-Mancha – Spain). The people who participated in this survey were the alpha users of the APOLLO project as they were selected during the Task 2.3 – Co-creation of Services process. The alpha users consist of three (3) farmers and one (1) crop consultant from each pilot area and helped in the development of the APOLLO services and platform by testing them at different phases. The farmers followed the evaluation plans guidelines that were provided to them by the AUA team (Task 6.3 leader) and are described in D6.1 -Pilot plan and evaluation methodology. Crop consultants were responsible for monitoring the proper execution of the evaluation plans and the monitoring of APOLLO platform services. The evaluation plans were developed for each crop and country and was based on the evaluation plans that were presented in D6.1 Pilot Plan and Evaluation Methodology. The APOLLO services that were evaluated per country and crop type are presented in the table below.

Table 2 Evaluation of APOLLO services for each country and crop

Country	Crop Type	Number of Fields	APOLLO services under evaluation			
			Tillage Scheduling	Irrigation Scheduling	Crop Growth Monitoring	Yield Estimation
Greece	Cotton	2	Yes (1/2)	Yes	Yes	Yes
Serbia	Maize	3	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Spain	Maize	2	No	Yes	Yes	Yes
	Wheat	1	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

2 APOLLO Platform Services Evaluation

2.1 Tillage Scheduling Service Evaluation

For the evaluation of APOLLO tillage scheduling service, the crop consultants of ACP and UPOR were responsible for monitoring and conducting the experiments in Greece and Serbia accordingly. The farmers followed the instructions of crop consultants and performed the tillage operations according to the experimental design. When comparing APOLLO tillage scheduling service with their current practices for the same type of tillage operation, farmers drove the same tractor with the same tillage equipment. This was done for eliminating the differences that could be presented in fuel consumption results due to use of different i) tractor models , ii) tillage implement and iii) driving behavior (Grisso et al., 2004; Stichter, 2012; Adewoyin and Ajav, 2013).

2.1.1 Greece

The evaluation of APOLLO tillage scheduling service took place in one field during November and December 2018 on ploughing (primary tillage operation). The farmer tilled using moldboard plough attached on his tractor. It is worth mentioning that the farmer tilled according to his experience on average soil conditions, while he followed the APOLLO tillage scheduling service when the soil conditions were good. The reason for waiting for the optimal soil conditions was that the time window for conducting this operation was too short due to the very rainy weather in the previous weeks. The results of the evaluation are presented in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1 Fuel consumption between current tillage practice and APOLLO Tillage Scheduling Service in Greece for primary tillage operations

Figure 2 Operation speed between current tillage practice and APOLLO Tillage Scheduling Service in Greece for primary tillage operations

Although the fuel savings weren't significant (1%) the farmer stated that the soil preparation was better following APOLLO tillage scheduling service compared to his tillage practice. Specifically, he mentioned that when following the current tillage practices the tractor was shaking during ploughing and the soil had big plough pans after finishing the operation. On the contrary, when he followed the APOLLO tillage scheduling service the tractor didn't present so high vibrations and the soil had finer quality. One other advantage of using the APOLLO tillage scheduling was that the tillage operation was conducted faster by 10%. This means that the farmers can increase their productivity in tillage operations and save labour costs. It is worth mentioning that the field conditions were not optimal, implying that the fuel savings could be higher, if the tillage operations have taken place in optimal soil conditions. However, a major shortcoming has to do with the time window of the operation, since the tillage operation was conducted with a delay of 40 days due to the rainy weather conditions and the farmer couldn't wait for the APOLLO platform for providing him optimal soil conditions for tillage. Moreover, the APOLLO tillage scheduling services did not indicate optimal conditions for tillage.

2.1.2 Serbia

Evaluation of tillage scheduling service took place in four different fields during April 2018 on secondary tillage operations (cultivator) on maize and soybean. The results of this evaluation are presented in Figure 3. The farmers tilled their fields according to APOLLO tillage scheduling service when they saw in APOLLO platform that the conditions for soil tillage were optimum in all cases. One of the things that they noticed was that the driving speed was improved when following APOLLO tillage advice in comparison with tilling the soil according to their experience.

Figure 3 Fuel consumption between current tillage practice and APOLLO Tillage Scheduling Service in Serbia for secondary tillage operations

The APOLLO tillage scheduling service presented significant fuel savings in all fields in comparison to current tillage scheduling practice. The fuel savings ranged between 7 to 32% with the **average fuel consumption** being 6.27 L/ha for the current tillage scheduling practice and 5.28 L/ha for the APOLLO tillage scheduling service. The tillage operation based on APOLLO tillage scheduling service presented 16% less fuel consumption compared to the current tillage scheduling practice. APOLLO tillage scheduling service experiments were conducted 5.5 days (4-11 days range) later, compared to the farmers' current tillage scheduling practice.

2.1.3 Spain

Main aim of the Spanish farmers was to compare the agreement between the APOLLO tillage scheduling service recommendations and their decision making on time for tillage operations. According to the results there was 83% agreement between the farmers decision making and the APOLLO tillage scheduling service recommendations regarding the time of tillage operations. It needs to be highlighted that Spanish farmers in the field test area are mainly applying no-tillage cultivation practices and it was too difficult to find farmers for the evaluation of APOLLO tillage scheduling service.

2.2 Irrigation Scheduling Service Evaluation

For the evaluation of APOLLO irrigation scheduling service, the crop consultants of ACP and AGRISAT were responsible for monitoring and conducting the experiments in Greece and Spain accordingly. It needs to be highlighted that AGRISAT already works with the farmers providing them irrigation advices based on satellite remote sensing. The farmers followed the instructions of crop consultants and performed the irrigation operations according to the experimental design.

2.2.1 Greece

The evaluation of irrigation scheduling service took place in two fields cultivated with cotton during 2018. The farmers were irrigating using public water pipelines from their local irrigation network. It is worth mentioning that precipitation during the evaluation period was very high (339 mm) and this resulted in decreased number of irrigation. Actually, the farmers conducted only one irrigation applying 40 m³/ha near the end of the irrigation period, while the APOLLO irrigation scheduling

service recommended them not to do this. The results of the irrigation evaluation experiments on cotton are presented in the figures below.

Figure 4 Total amount of water applied between current irrigation practice and APOLLO irrigation scheduling service for cotton field 1

Figure 5 Total amount of water applied between current irrigation practice and APOLLO irrigation scheduling service for cotton field 2

The main crop water needs were covered through precipitation and only a small percent through irrigation. It needs to be highlighted that the sowing of cotton in the second field was delayed almost 30 days due to the high precipitation, resulting to be harvested later compared to the first field. In the case of the trial plots that follow APOLLO recommendations, there was no suggestion for irrigation compared to the current farmers practice which included irrigation for one day. Thus, the APOLLO irrigation scheduling service achieved 10.5% water savings on average for the two cotton fields when compared with the current irrigation practice. Finally, during the evaluation period there was 99% agreement between the farmers current practice and APOLLO irrigation scheduling advices.

2.2.2 Serbia

There was no use of APOLLO irrigation scheduling service in Serbia, because all farmers cultivate rainfed crops. This means that they do not use irrigation systems for water application.

2.2.3 Spain

The evaluation of irrigation scheduling service took place in two fields, one cultivated with maize and one cultivated with wheat during 2018. The farmers were irrigating using private irrigation systems. The results of the irrigation evaluation experiments on maize and wheat are presented below.

2.2.3.1 Maize

Figure 6 Total amount of water applied between current irrigation practice and APOLLO irrigation scheduling service for a maize field in Spain

The maize received high number of irrigation operations due to the low amount of precipitation. However, the savings at APOLLO irrigation scheduling plot were not high enough (5%) compared to the current irrigation practices plot. This was because the farmer was already using satellite remote sensing data for irrigation scheduling through Agrisat and the result can be explained through various ways (e.g. the intrinsic spatial variability of the field) and not because of the APOLLO irrigation service. Thus, a safe conclusion on the impact of APOLLO irrigation scheduling service on this maize field cannot be taken and further trials are needed.

2.2.3.2 Wheat

Figure 7 Total amount of water applied between current irrigation practice and APOLLO irrigation scheduling service for a wheat field in Spain

The wheat received almost half of its water needs through precipitation and the other half through irrigation. However, the water savings of APOLLO irrigation scheduling plot were not high enough (3.5%) compared to the current irrigation practices plot. This was because the farmer was already using satellite remote sensing data for irrigation scheduling through Agrisat and the result can be explained by various reasons (e.g. the intrinsic spatial variability of the field) and not because of the APOLLO irrigation service. Thus, a safe conclusion on the impact of APOLLO irrigation scheduling service on irrigated wheat crop cannot be taken and further trials are needed.

2.3 Crop Growth Monitoring Products for Tillage and Irrigation Scheduling Services Evaluation

Aim of the crop growth monitoring products was to assess the crop vigor parameters in relation to the application of the different APOLLO platform recommendations. For doing this, the crop growth monitoring products were used from the APOLLO platform for the different experimental plots. The validation of the crop growth monitoring products was addressed on the activities that took place in WP3 - Earth Observation Data Products and are reported in D6.4 Pilot data validation report. Specifically, the maximum values of biomass, CI-index, LAI and NDVI were used for statistical analysis. The statistical analysis was conducted using the StatGraphics Centurion software (Statgraphics Technologies, Inc., Virginia, USA).

2.3.1 Greece

2.3.1.1 Cotton

The results of the APOLLO platform's crop growing products on the cotton field evaluation experiments are presented in the figures below.

Figure 8 Accumulated biomass among the different experimental plots of two cotton fields

Figure 9 Max CI-Index among the different experimental plots of two cotton fields

Figure 10 Max LAI among the different experimental plots of two cotton fields

Figure 11 Max NDVI among the different experimental plots of two cotton fields

The statistical analysis did not present any significant difference of the APOLLO crop growth monitoring products (namely biomass, CI-index, LAI and NDVI) among the parcels which were following different advices regarding tillage and irrigation scheduling. Consequently, the savings that can be achieved by using the APOLLO platform could not impact crop growth of cotton crop.

2.3.2 Serbia

The results of the APOLLO platform’s crop growing products of the field evaluation experiments in Serbia for maize are presented in the figures below.

2.3.2.1 Maize

Figure 12 Accumulated biomass among the different experimental plots of three maize fields

Figure 13 Max CI-Index among the different experimental plots of three maize fields

Figure 14 Max LAI among the different experimental plots of three maize fields

Figure 15 Max NDVI among the different experimental plots of three maize fields

The statistical analysis did not present any significant difference among the different treatments regarding all the APOLLO crop growth monitoring products (namely biomass, CI-index, LAI and NDVI). Consequently, the savings that can be achieved on tillage operations by using the APOLLO platform did not present any significant impact on crop growth of maize crop.

2.3.2.2 Soybean

The results of the APOLLO platform's crop growing products of the field evaluation experiments in Serbia for soybean are presented in the figures below (Figure 16 and Figure 17) .

Figure 16 Max NDVI, LAI and CI-index among the different experimental plots of soybean field

Figure 17 Accumulated biomass among the different experimental plots of three maize fields

The APOLLO tillage scheduling plot presented higher values in all crop growth parameters when compared with the current tillage practice. The highest difference was presented in accumulated biomass which was almost 26 %.

2.3.3 Spain

The results of the APOLLO platform's crop growing products of the field evaluation experiments in Spain are presented in the figures below.

2.3.3.1 Maize

Figure 18 Accumulated biomass among the different experimental plots of one maize field

Figure 19 Max CI-Index among the different experimental plots of one maize field

Figure 20 Max LAI among the different experimental plots of one maize field

Figure 21 Max NDVI among the different experimental plots of one maize field

The APOLLO crop growth monitoring evaluation on maize crop in Spain did not present any significant differences among the various products of the APOLLO platform. However, further evaluation is needed in more fields in order to have results that are more accurate.

2.3.3.2 Wheat

Figure 22 Accumulated biomass among the different experimental plots of one wheat field

Figure 23 Max CI-Index among the different experimental plots of one wheat field

Figure 24 Max LAI among the different experimental plots of one wheat field

Figure 25 Max NDVI among the different experimental plots of one wheat field

The results of APOLLO crop growth monitoring evaluation on wheat crop in Spain, presented no significant differences among the various products of the APOLLO platform. However, further evaluation is needed in more fields in order to present more solid results.

2.4 Crop Yield Estimation Products for Tillage and Irrigation Scheduling Services Evaluation

The crop yield estimation product was used for evaluating the tillage and irrigation scheduling services. The validation of crop yield estimation service is presented in D6.7 - Validation Report. Main aim was to understand how the different recommendations of the APOLLO platform would impact crop production.

2.4.1 Greece

2.4.1.1 Cotton

Figure 26 Estimated yield comparison among the different experimental plots for two cotton fields

Based on the results there are no significant differences between the APOLLO tillage and irrigation scheduling services with the current agricultural practices regarding cotton yield for the two fields. Consequently, cotton producers can benefit in terms of water, fuel and cost savings by following the APOLLO platform recommendations.

2.4.2 Serbia

2.4.2.1 Maize

Figure 27 Estimated yield comparison among the different experimental plots for three maize fields

Based on the statistical analysis, there are no significant differences between the APOLLO tillage scheduling service plots with the current agricultural practices plots regarding maize yield for the three fields although. Consequently, maize producers can benefit by following the APOLLO platform recommendations and achieve important savings in water and at the same time achieve the same or higher crop yields.

2.4.2.2 Soybean

Figure 28 Estimated yield comparison among the different experimental plots for the soybean field

The yield estimation service presented that the APOLLO tillage scheduling plot achieved higher yield by almost 20%, when compared with plot that followed current tillage scheduling practices. Consequently, soybean growers can achieve higher yields when following the APOLLO tillage scheduling service due to better crop growth while at the same time have important fuel savings and consequently reduce their cultivation costs.

2.4.3 Spain

2.4.3.1 Maize

Figure 29 Estimated yield comparison among the different experimental plots for one maize field

2.4.3.2 Wheat

Figure 30 Estimated yield comparison among the different experimental plots for one wheat field

There was 3.3% difference in yield estimations among the two different plots with the APOLLO irrigation scheduling plot achieving higher estimated yield (12.49 tn/ha). However, further evaluation is needed in more fields in order to present safe results for wheat crop.

3 Conclusions

APOLLO tillage scheduling service can help farmers achieve up to 32% savings in fuel consumption and increase their productivity by tilling more area in less time. However, savings can vary according to each tillage operation (primary or secondary) and the driver's attitude. Moreover, APOLLO tillage scheduling service helped producers that followed its advices to achieve the same or higher yields while achieving significant fuel and cost savings on tillage operations.

APOLLO irrigation scheduling service presented up to 11% water savings in cotton fields while the water savings in Spain were less than 5% on wheat and maize crops. Although there was high precipitation in Greece during cotton growing period, the water savings were higher compared to Spain, which they were facing a very dry weather, especially during maize growing period. This can be explained by the fact that the current farmer practices can affect greatly the results on potential water savings. In our case, the use of satellite remote sensing for irrigation scheduling, as the current irrigation practice from Spanish farmers confirmed the water savings that are presented in the scientific literature compared to no-use of satellite remote sensing cultivation practices from Greek farmers. Due to this, the savings that the APOLLO platform can help Spanish farmers achieve are limited compared to the Greek farmers.

The aforementioned results presented that both APOLLO tillage and irrigation scheduling services can present significant savings (in fuel and water respectively) to the farmers without affecting crop growth and expected yield. Thus, the APOLLO platform can be a promising solution/tool that will help farmers on achieving a more sustainable crop production. However, more field trials are needed for more crops and for many years in order to assess better the true potential of the APOLLO platform.

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